

TODAY'S REFORMS TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION - AS A FACTOR OF SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT

Rohila Saparboy qizi Xidirboyeva

English teacher at TMC Institute in Tashkent

ABSTRACT

This article puts forward new ideas about the reforms being implemented today to improve the quality of higher education - as a factor of social development. In addition, extensive foreign experience in improving the education system and its quality was studied. As a result of these analyses, proposals and recommendations were developed to improve the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Higher education, education, education and upbringing, teacher, youth, reforms, financial independence, quality of education.

Introduction. Today, work is increasingly being done to improve the quality of education all over the world. Since the development and prospects of society largely depend on personnel, there is a growing tendency to understand that education plays a key role in this. From this perspective, achieving the quality and effectiveness of education is important. We can see that various approaches to understanding the philosophical essence of the reforms implemented in our country in recent years have been active in the last decades. In particular, there are many scientific studies aimed at cognitive analysis.

Since the first years of independence, the development of the education system in our country has risen to the level of state policy, ensuring that our children acquire modern knowledge and professions in conditions that meet world standards, grow up as physically and spiritually mature people, realize their abilities and talents, intellectual potential, and cultivate feelings of loyalty and selflessness to the Motherland in the hearts of our youth. Over the past 5 years, positive changes have been taking place in the higher education system as a result of numerous innovations and reforms. In order to ensure the implementation of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6108 dated November 6, 2020 “On measures to develop the spheres of education, upbringing and science in the new period of development of Uzbekistan”, a

number of tasks have been set for the development of the spheres of education and science. It is not for nothing that it is said that the New Uzbekistan begins from the school threshold. Today, all spheres of life in the New Uzbekistan have become a field of deep reforms. In this process, it is impossible not to speak enthusiastically about the changes in the education system, which is considered the basis of the social sphere. In recent years, practical work on organizing all stages of the education system in our country based on modern requirements has entered a decisive stage. As our President noted: “We all know that the cornerstone of development, the force that makes a country powerful and a nation great, is science, education and upbringing. Our tomorrow, the bright prospects of our Motherland, are closely related, first of all, to the education system and the upbringing we give to our children.” The reforms in the higher education system that have been implemented in our country in recent years are significant in that they are ultimately aimed at improving the quality of higher education. This, in turn, requires further improvement of the system of training highly qualified personnel that meets the high requirements and recognized standards of civil society formation, as well as the study of advanced modern technologies and innovative educational and upbringing processes in order to fundamentally reform and deepen the modernization processes of the education system.

As is known, the concept of quality of education received its international name at the World Conference on Higher Education and its Further Improvement in 1998 in Paris. At this conference, with the participation of 29 countries, it was emphasized that ensuring the quality of education is a long-term strategic task of educational institutions.

There is no single approach or methodology in the scientific and philosophical literature to explain the philosophical essence of the concept of quality of education. According to theoreticians, philosophers and practitioners who study the higher education system and its processes, it is very difficult to give a single definition of the quality of education. Because there are a number of objective and subjective factors affecting it, which make it difficult to give a single definition. That is, it is clear to all of us that factors such as the characteristics of each region, the mentality of the nation, its historical roots, the stages of the formation of the education system over a long history, the influence of cultures and civilizations cannot fail to have their impact. Also, taking into account that there is no ideal education system in the world, the reforms being carried out in this regard and the day-to-day development of social relations in society,

life sets new and new requirements for us, which requires constant improvement of the "Quality of Education". The emergence of new discoveries and inventions even creates the need for social changes in education. Experts include the following factors in ensuring the quality of education: a) educational institutions; b) professors and teachers; c) students, graduates; d) parents; d) consumers, personnel customers. In 1998, the World Conference on Higher Education organized by UNESCO adopted the "World Declaration on Higher Education for the 21st Century". In this declaration, the following definition was given to the concept of quality of education: "Quality is a multidisciplinary concept in higher education, which includes all functions and types of activities, educational and academic programs, scientific research and scholarships, the provision of educational institutions with qualified and qualified personnel, students who work independently on themselves, buildings, structures, material and technical base, devices and equipment, and employment of graduates." If we turn to the opinions of scientists, Jim Collins emphasizes: "The leaders of large companies began the process of reorganization by recruiting the right people for their team and getting rid of the unnecessary. Then they chose which direction to swim. The main idea is that personnel decides everything, the word who is more important than the word what. Because personnel is a strategy, an organizational structure, a tactic. Companies today need to create their own foundations to move to a new quality stage. In my opinion, the fundamental answer to this question is the issue of personnel. In a word, these thoughts of Jim Collins are consistent with the statement that the quality of personnel training today should correspond to the quality of education. For this, it is necessary to train highly qualified personnel capable of conducting innovative activities in educational institutions. In a word, without more thorough training of personnel and without appreciating them, one cannot achieve success in any field.

The development of science, technology and engineering in modern society imposes on the higher education system the following tasks: a) high-quality and guaranteed training of personnel; b) ensuring the mobility of professors and teachers and students; d) improving the methods of evaluating educational programs in the activities of higher education institutions, and others. In our country, a number of legal and regulatory documents have been developed and actively implemented in practice over the past three years to raise the higher education system to a quality level. If we pay attention to the philosophical essence and content of the priority tasks set out in the

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” of October 8, 2019, as one of such important strategic documents, we will witness that the main goal is to determine the priority areas of systemic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, to raise the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high spiritual and moral qualities, independent thinking to a qualitatively new level, to modernize higher education, and to develop the social sphere and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies. Based on the purpose of the Decree, the following tasks are envisaged to be implemented on a consistent basis. Namely: "developing public-private partnerships in the field of higher education, increasing the coverage of higher education by more than 50 percent based on the organization of the activities of state and non-state higher education institutions in the regions, creating a healthy competitive environment in the field; introducing advanced standards of higher education based on international experience, including a gradual transition from education focused on acquiring theoretical knowledge in curricula to an education system focused on the formation of practical skills; raising the content of higher education to a qualitatively new level, establishing a system for training highly qualified personnel who can make a worthy contribution to the sustainable development of the social sphere and economic sectors, and find their place in the labor market" are among these tasks.

It can be said that the active implementation of the tasks set out in the decree in the future will undoubtedly serve to increase the quality of the higher education system, as well as to increase the prestige and reputation of our country in the world and achieve the level of development of the leading countries of the world. Also, by increasing the coverage of higher education of our country's population, as envisaged in the decree, one of the basic laws of philosophy, namely "quantitative changes with qualitative changes", will establish the cultivation of quality personnel and develop a healthy competitive environment among personnel, which ultimately will serve to meet the needs of society for quality personnel.

For this, it is necessary to increase the efficiency of the educational process and further improve the quality of education by introducing modern pedagogical technologies into the educational process. In this regard, President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev gave the following instructions: “...in my opinion, it is necessary to solve two main

tasks: first, it is necessary to significantly strengthen the material and technical base of scientific institutions at the level of advanced foreign centers and in accordance with the requirements of scientists. In this, of course, the needs of the state and its target objectives must be taken into account;

- second, it is necessary to develop and implement specific measures for comprehensive support of academicians, including material incentives,” indicating the need, and tasks were set for the development and implementation of a system of specific measures in this regard.

Important practical steps have been taken to expand the participation of the higher education system in solving the issues of developing the higher education system, providing our country's consistently developing economy with highly qualified personnel, and strategically comprehensive development of all regions and sectors.

Psychologist T.V. Volodina noted that “in order to improve the professional activity of a teacher, it is necessary to perceive the pedagogical process as a system”. Thus, the quality of personnel being trained in the higher education system largely depends on the professional dedication of professors and teachers working in the higher education system.

If we study the existing problems in the higher education system of Uzbekistan based on statistical data, we will witness the existence of social problems that are waiting for an adequate solution. If we analyze as of January 1, 2013, the coverage of the number of students in the higher education system was 9%, which is low compared to regional and international standards and sharply differs from the situation at the primary and secondary levels of the education system of Uzbekistan (where almost 100% of the school-age population is covered). The centralized planning system determines both the number of students in higher education institutions (universities and institutes) and their fields of study. The number of places in higher education institutions in each direction is determined by state resolutions, and students are selected based on the results of national tests conducted by the State Testing Center under the Cabinet of Ministers. With almost 100% coverage of the secondary education system and 9% of higher education, 9 out of 10 school graduates cannot enter university, the demand for higher education is high, and competition for each place offered at universities exceeds 6 people. 60% of students entering universities are men (in recent years, the share of women in universities has decreased, unlike other countries in the region. There were

various reasons for this). Although such issues have led to partial changes in the last three years, they still do not fully meet international standards. This can be attributed to the fact that a number of bureaucratic obstacles still remain. Even the modernizations of 2019 could not stop the shortage of highly educated personnel in Uzbekistan. It is worth noting that graduates of the higher education system often do not work in their specialty (for example, only 57% of graduates of pedagogical universities are employed in the education sector, while in the construction sector, construction occupies three-quarters of all positions intended for graduates of higher education institutions, the rest are occupied by graduates of other universities). The low level of coverage and weak relations between employers, industry and universities also limit the economy's ability to innovate, adapt technologies and create added value. Clearly, much work needs to be done to prepare universities to meet the demands of a changing economy and to bridge the gap between supply and demand for university graduates.

REFERENCES:

1. Kadamovich, Y. J., Muzaffarovna, I. G., Maxmudovich, Y. B., Boxtiyarovna, S.S., & Xabibullayevich, S. S. (2020). Social justice as a condition of socio-spiritual stability in society. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(5), 816-818.
2. Ramatov, J. S., Baratov, R. O., Sultanov, S. H., Kushakov, F. A., Valiyev, L. A., & Xasanov, M. N. (2022). Hozirgi davrda ijtimoiy adolat haqidagi ilmiy-falsafiy qarashlarning o'ziga xos talqini. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(9), 647-656.
3. Abdumannapovna, M. D., & Juraevna, N. N. (2022). The role of social institutions in the development of young people. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(6), 67-70.
4. Ramatov, J. S., Hasanov, M., & Nazarova, N. J. (2022). Mediamadaniyat va axborotdan foydalanishning intellektual ta'lim tizimini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(6), 984-988.